

**ADMINISTRATION OF NIGERIAN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN THE 21ST
CENTURY: CHALLENGES AND WAY FORWARD**

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Abstract

The complexities of 21st-century tertiary education administration in Nigeria pose a formidable challenge to administrators, resulting from a confluence of personal, environmental, governmental, policy-related, and other external factors that impede the development of the country's educational sector. To mitigate these challenges, research plays a crucial role in advancing the growth of Nigeria's tertiary institutions. This study aimed to explore the challenges faced by tertiary education in Nigeria and provide possible solutions. This research investigated the challenges facing tertiary educations in Nigeria as well as highlighting possible solutions. The study used a descriptive survey design and administered a self-created questionnaire to gather participants' opinions on the challenges facing tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The questionnaire was used to obtain responses from the participants, and its reliability was determined to be .75, demonstrating the usefulness and internal consistency of the instrument. The data collected was analyzed using frequency distribution, mean, and standard deviation. The results showed a weighted mean of 2.98, 3.27, and 3.38 for research questions 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The study concluded that Nigerian tertiary institutions are facing significant issues that need prompt attention and resolution.

Introduction

The administration of higher educational institutions has been somewhat challenging for 21st-century administrators. This is due to a fusion of issues ranging from personal, environmental, governmental indifference, policy somersaults, and lots of other external influences that cumulatively affect the progress of the country's educational sector as a whole; in turn, the adverse effects reflected on the level of output of higher education administrators.

In Africa and around the world, there has been growing reforms in the tertiary educational sector. This is obvious in the manner that tertiary institutions around the world in general are consistent in reporting their gains and obvious development (Dawkins, Hurley and Noonan, 2019; Rust and James, 2021). However, the current situation in the Nigerian sector of tertiary education call for concern as there has been a stunted growth in the sector for several years; this does not mean that there has been no development whatsoever in Nigeria tertiary education space. Nevertheless, Nigeria being at the core of Africa populism has some role to play in ensuring that its quality of tertiary education is equivalent or much similar to the one obtainable in many countries of the world. Oyebade and Dike (2013) asserted that for many stakeholders in the tertiary education space, these concerns are obvious as evident in the persistent demands of tertiary institutions' unions (ASUU, NASU, COEASU, SSANIP, ASUP amongst others) to restructure the sector. These Unions have constantly identified the rot in the system and incessantly request that a state of emergency be declared on the management of tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria.

The escalating enrolment in Nigerian educational institutions presents a stark reality; the ratio of staff to students is alarmingly low. According to Okoye and Anachuna (2021), many higher education institutions, particularly those owned by the federal and state governments, are admitting more students than the available pool of qualified lecturers and necessary facilities such as lecture halls, laboratories, and instructional materials can accommodate. This results in a recurrent overshoot of the institution's 'carrying capacity (which is the maximum number of students that can be supported for quality education based on available resources). This crucial issue demands immediate attention and resolution to ensure that Nigeria's educational institutions can provide an optimal learning environment for their students.

The significance of higher education institutions in fostering human capital development and providing skilled manpower for various sectors of society has been well-established. These institutions have been recognized as the backbone of socio-economic progress and political stability,

serving as a catalyst for individuals to reach their full potential and achieve their aspirations (Ogunode and Musa, 2020). As advocates for the development of tertiary education, it is crucial to appreciate the impact these institutions have on shaping the future of the nation. Investing in human capital through higher education is a crucial aspect of ensuring economic growth and sustainability. In today's rapidly evolving world, it is imperative that individuals have the necessary skills and knowledge to meet the demands of a rapidly-changing workforce. Higher education institutions play a vital role in providing students with the education and training necessary to meet these demands, equipping them with the skills to succeed in the competitive world. Moreover, the impact of higher education extends beyond the economic sphere. It also plays a crucial role in shaping the political and social landscape of a nation. By fostering critical thinking, civic engagement, and social awareness, higher education institutions help create a more informed and engaged citizenry, promoting political stability and socio-economic progress.

In continuance, the collective consciousness of society has long been shaped to view education as a key tool in freeing individuals from the shackles of poverty, ignorance, and illiteracy. This perception is rooted in the belief that education serves as a path towards self-actualization, improved socio-economic standing, and exposure to a diverse array of perspectives. Research supports the critical role that educational institutions have played in addressing a multitude of societal issues, such as corruption, bribery, ignorance, conservatism, disease, malnutrition, superstition, tribalism, nepotism, political instability, unemployment, and economic stagnation (Uddin, 2013; Yusha'u et al., 2021).

There has been a growing recognition of the economic value of tertiary educational institutions. As highlighted by Howell, Unterhalter, and Oketch (2020), these institutions are crucial for fostering knowledge creation, dissemination, and application, as well as for developing technical and professional capabilities. It has been repeatedly emphasized that tertiary education is vital in nurturing the intellectual capacity required for knowledge production and utilization, as well as promoting lifelong learning (Chankseliani and McCowan, 2021). Thus, it becomes imperative for governments

and other relevant stakeholders to take an active role in managing and enhancing the quality of tertiary education to meet the challenges ahead. The study of Nigerian tertiary education by Ofojebe and Chukwuma (2015) highlights the important role that this sector plays in the development of the country. Tertiary education is viewed as the cornerstone of national progress and transformation, providing the necessary manpower and skills to drive productivity, prosperity, and scientific and technological advancement. Through their training and expertise, tertiary institutions are able to shape the future of the country and lead the way in terms of communication expansion, wealth creation, and healthy living. The importance of this sector cannot be overstated and it is essential that it continues to receive the support and investment necessary to maintain its vital role in national development.

Ekundayo and Ajayi (2009) emphasize the crucial role of tertiary education in shaping the future of a nation. They assert that this level of education has a significant impact on not only the personal development of individuals but also on the overall progress and prosperity of society. Through providing high-level, relevant training and fostering the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills, tertiary education empowers individuals to become self-reliant, productive members of society. Additionally, it has the potential to promote unity and understanding both domestically and globally, as well as drive scholarly advancements and encourage community service. The authors highlight the multifaceted benefits of tertiary education, emphasizing its crucial role in shaping the future of a nation.

Given the crucial role that tertiary educational systems play in advancing the development of society, it would be reasonable to assume that such a vital system would be free of challenges. However, this is far from the truth, as numerous studies and articles have documented the persistent issues plaguing higher education in Nigeria. These problems have been attributed to the mismanagement of educational institutions and the involvement of various actors. Addressing the challenges facing tertiary education in Nigeria requires a comprehensive understanding of the problems and a collaborative effort by researchers and stakeholders to implement effective solutions. Famade,

Omiyale, and Adebola (2015) emphasize the need for further research on the challenges facing the educational sector, with a specific focus on tertiary institutions. This research delved into exploring the challenges faced by Nigerian tertiary institutions in the 21st century and offer potential solutions.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to highlight the challenges facing tertiary educational institutions in the country. Other specific objectives of the research include:

- To understand the factors militating against the development of educational institutions in Nigeria?
- To ascertain the importance and role of tertiary education in proffering solutions to the modern challenges facing the country.
- To unravel solutions as regards the challenges facing educational institutions.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- What are the factors militating against the development of educational institutions in Nigeria?
- What are the roles educational institutions can play in advancing the progress of the nation?
- What are the solutions to the challenges facing educational institutions in the country?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Administration of Educational Institutions in Nigeria

Administration refers to the process of organizing resources to attain organizational goals. This systematic approach encompasses the utilization of both human and material resources to achieve the objectives set by the organization (Robbins, DeCenzo, and Coulter, 2020). Similarly, administration is the application and the deployment of organizational resources towards the achievement of

organizational goals. Effective administration is essential to the achievement of institutional objectives, and the competency of the school management plays a significant role in the success of the school system. The efficient arrangement, monitoring, and control of lecturers, students, non-teaching staff, and resources are crucial to maximizing the output of the system (Robbins, DeCenzo, and Coulter, 2020).

Nwankwoala (2016) defines educational administration as a broad term encompassing several processes such as planning, coordinating, controlling, and contributing to policy formulation. The leader of the educational organization plays a crucial role in meticulously planning programs and events to attain set objectives. Educational administration refers to the management of educational institutions and the direction, leadership, and supervision of individual efforts towards achieving institutional goals (Nwankwoala, 2016). In Nigeria, the purpose of educational administration is to integrate and coordinate all educational resources for the attainment of the educational institution's goals and objectives (Adeniyi and Adekunle, 2019).

The task of managing a tertiary educational institution is a complex and collaborative effort that requires the involvement of various stakeholders (Meenyinikor, Timi-Johnson, & Chux-Nyeche, 2014). Within the system, there are numerous divisions, faculties, departments, units, or centers that each contribute to the management and administration of the institution (Okoli, 2015). The decision-making process in tertiary educational institutions is typically based on a committee system, in which multiple actors and departments have input and influence (Akindutire, 2004). The management of these institutions is divided into internal and external management. The internal management is responsible for the day-to-day operations of the institution, with a portfolio that varies depending on the type of tertiary institution. The external management, on the other hand, serves as a supervisory and regulatory body for the institution (Meenyinikor et al., 2014).

The Internal Management: The internal management members are directly involved in the day-to-day running of the institution. Their portfolios depend on the form of higher education being rendered by the institution. On a general note, and irrespective of the institution, the nomenclature for the position of Registrar, Bursar, Librarian is constant. For the Chief Executive Head in the institution, the Universities are to be headed by the Vice-Chancellor, Rector for Polytechnics and Monotechnics, and Provost for Colleges of Education. According to the structure of educational institutions, the highest level of management is occupied by the Governing Council. The council holds a crucial responsibility in overseeing the administration of the institution, including setting goals, formulating policies, fostering staff development, maintaining discipline, approving budgets, and maintaining communication with the government.

The External Management: At the external level, the Federal Government controls university education in Nigeria through the National Universities Commission (NUC). The NUC aims to maintain high standards and adequate funding for universities, and performs tasks such as course accreditation, program approval, and monitoring of academic standards. The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) oversees technical education programs, while the National Commission for Colleges of Education supervises Colleges of Education. These Commissions regulate and monitor the activities of their respective institutions.

21st Century Demands on Nigerian Educational Institutions

Udem, Ejike, and Okpalibekwe (2021) highlight the importance of education in a nation's development, including in Nigeria. The tertiary level of education in the country consists of both university and non-university sectors, such as polytechnics, monotechnics, and colleges of education. This sector offers a range of educational opportunities, including undergraduate, graduate, and vocational programs (Ogunode, Wama, and Akhmedov, 2020). The National Policy on Education

(FGN, 2013) defines tertiary education as post-secondary education and encompasses institutions such as universities, polytechnics, colleges of technology, and colleges of education, among others. Isuku and Emunemu (2009) argue that tertiary education has a significant impact on national productivity and can improve the standard of living and stimulate local economic growth. According to Ogunode, *et al.* (2020), the demands the challenges of the 21st century placed on Nigeria educational institutions are enough of an excuse to warrant a change in how tertiary institutions are being run.

Additionally, the pace of development in the present century is unsurprising and as such tertiary institutions in the country have to meet with the demands of the present century to stand a chance or have a shot at inclusion in the leagues of top institutions in the world. The ever-changing face of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has, even more necessitated it for institutions to move beyond their comfort zone and adopt new measures in running the institutions. The unexpected Covid - 19 pandemic necessitated tertiary educational institutions to shift grounds from the known and rigid conventional methods to more flexible policies.

In the aspect of teaching and learning, Covid - 19 has affected the traditional classroom activities of face-to-face teaching and learning involving lecturers and students in tertiary institutions as well as the effective management of institutions (Ogunode, Ndubuisi and Terfa, 2021). It has forced the adoption of online teaching and learning which until now not presently practiced in Nigerian tertiary institutions, especially government-owned institutions. With the challenges faced during the pandemic, it is safe to say that measures adopted to ease the process of administration has come to stay.

Challenges Facing The Administration of Tertiary Educational System in Nigeria

Nigeria's educational administration is facing numerous challenges, both internally and externally. These challenges have been the focus of many administration researchers who have identified

recurrent issues in the sector. This study aims to explore these challenges and offer solutions to overcome them. According to Ogunode et al. (2020), one of the major challenges is the appointment of inexperienced officials to lead the country's educational institutions. Effective leadership is essential for good school administration and management, however, many educational leaders in public institutions in Nigeria are not well-equipped for the role. Other challenges include a lack of data for planning, insufficient funding and personnel, inadequate infrastructure, and corruption within the institutions.

The challenges facing educational administration in Nigeria have been well documented by various researchers. Jacob, Terhemba, and Ndubuisi (2021) found that insufficient funding, shortage of professional teachers, subpar infrastructure, corruption, insecurity, weak administrators, lack of data, policy instability, strike actions, and brain-drain are the main challenges preventing effective educational administration in Nigeria. Oyebade and Dike (2013) highlighted the discontinuity in national policy and the impact of political interference on educational administration. They also pointed to the issues of localization in academics and student admission, inadequate infrastructure, poor supervision and monitoring by regulators, inadequate manpower leading to ineffective regulation of the teaching profession, overcrowded lecture rooms, and other challenges. The frequent policy changes and political interference have resulted in abandoned education projects and inconsistent education policies. Additionally, the issue of unqualified teachers and overcrowded lecture rooms have also contributed to the challenges faced by educational administration in Nigeria. These challenges, if not addressed, may hinder the development of the nation and negatively impact the future of students in the country.

Challenges to educational administration in Nigeria have been prevalent for years, according to various researchers. The effects of student militancy and violent unionism have resulted in the closure of tertiary institutions (Akindutire, 2004). The government's low priority for education has led to a shortage of funds and declining facilities, such as libraries and laboratories (Aina, 2007). Autonomy

and academic freedom in tertiary institutions have been ongoing issues (Babalola et al., 2007), and cultism among students presents a dangerous threat to academic activities (Smah, 2007; Eche, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive survey method to assess the opinions of the participants in order to determine the challenges faced by tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The study population consisted staff on level 13 and above in administration line (Registry, Bursary, etc.) and level 7 and above for academics from the selected tertiary institutions (University of Ibadan, The Polytechnic, Ibadan, and Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo). A convenient and proportionate random sampling procedure was employed and one hundred and ninety seven (197) staff (minimum of 60 participants from each institution) was selected for participation in the study. The researchers designed and constructed the research instrument for the study and had it validated by two experts. The questionnaire was called the Administration Development Scale (ADS) and consisted of 20 items rated on a modified 4-point Likert scale. The reliability of the instrument was established using the split-half method and a pilot test was conducted with 30 staff from the Emmanuel Alayande College of Education. The questionnaire is in four sections. Section 1 is the demographic information, section 2 for challenges confronting educational institutions, section 3 for roles educational institutions can play in advancing the development of the nation, section 4 comprised open-ended questions focused on possible solutions to the challenges being faced by tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The results showed a high degree of consistency and dependability, with a reliability coefficient of $r = .75$. The final versions of the questionnaire were distributed to the participants in person, collected after completion, and analyzed using frequency distribution, mean and standard deviation.

Results and Discussion

TABLE 1: RESPONSE ON CHALLENGES CONFRONTING TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS

Items	SA Freq(%)	A Freq(%)	D Freq(%)	SD Freq(%)	Mean ± SD
Inadequate funding contributes to poor educational quality in Nigeria	73(37.1)	117(59.4)	2(1)	5(2.5)	3.30 ± 0.62
Non adherence to quality assurance impede social transformation of education	46(23.4)	92(46.7)	54(27.4)	5(2.5)	2.90 ± 0.77
Administrative recklessness is a major challenge to educational quality	83(42.1)	95(48.2)	11(5.6)	8(4.1)	3.28 ± 0.74
Reckless government policies affect the progress of tertiary institution	23(11.7)	118(59.9)	56(28.4)	0(0)	2.83 ± 0.61
Non commitment of government to confronting challenges in the educational sector	65(33)	77(39.1)	41(20.8)	14(7.1)	2.97 ± 0.90
Non-meritorious standard of recruitment impede social transformation of education and quality	31(15.7)	111(56.3)	36(18.3)	19(9.6)	2.78 ± 0.82
Amenities such as electricity, water, good hostel accommodation and medical care are also inadequate	32(16.2)	112(56.9)	36(18.3)	17(8.9)	2.80 ± 0.81
Weighted Mean =2.98					

Table 1 above shows the responses of the respondents on the challenges confronting tertiary institutions. The results show that a large majority (59.4%) of respondents "Agree" that inadequate funding contributes to poor educational quality in Nigeria. 37.1% of respondents "Strongly Agree" with this statement while only 1% "Disagree" and 2.5% "Strongly Disagree". The results show that almost half (46.7%) of the

respondents "Agree" that non-adherence to quality assurance impairs the social transformation of education, while 23.4% "Strongly Agree" with this statement. 27.4% of respondents "Disagree" and 2.5% "Strongly Disagree". Responses of participants on the statement "Administrative recklessness is a major challenge to educational quality." 42.1% of participants strongly agreed with the statement, 48.2% agreed with the statement, 5.6% disagreed with the statement, and 4.1% strongly disagreed with the statement. The table revealed respondents believed that reckless government policies affect the progress of tertiary institutions. Out of a total of 197 respondents, 11.7% strongly agreed, 59.9% agreed, 28.4% disagreed, and 0% strongly disagreed with the statement. The results also indicate that there is a belief among the surveyed population that the government is not fully committed to addressing the challenges in the educational sector. 33% of the respondents "Strongly Agree" with this statement, while 39.1% "Agree", 20.8% "Disagree" and 7.1% "Strongly Disagree". For the statement "non-meritorious standard of recruitment impede social transformation of education and quality, 15.7% chose "Strongly Agree," 56.3% chose "Agree," 18.3% chose "Disagree," and 9.6% chose "Strongly Disagree. The results of a survey or study indicate that there is a perception among respondents that the lack of basic amenities such as electricity, water, good hostel accommodation and medical care contribute to poor quality in the education system. Out of the total number of respondents, 56.9% agreed with this statement, while 16.2% strongly agreed, 18.3% were neutral, and 8.9% disagreed. These results are in line with the study of (Ogunode and Musa, 2020; Jacob, Jegede and Musa, 2021; Ogunode, Akinjobi and Musa, 2022)

TABLE 2: ROLE OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION IN THE PROGRESS OF THE NATION

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean ± SD
	Freq(%)	Freq(%)	Freq(%)	Freq(%)	
Inculcation of national resources	121(61.4)	66(33.5)	5(2.5)	5(2.5)	3.53 ± 0.67
Acquisition of appropriate skills and the development of social abilities	58(29.4)	122(61.9)	13(6.6)	4(2)	3.18 ± 0.63
Reduction of social vices	45(22.8)	118(59.9)	31(15.7)	3(1.5)	3.04 ± 0.66
Training the mind in the understanding of the world around	73(37.1)	122(61.9)	2(1)	0(0)	3.36 ± 0.50
Weighted Mean =3.27					

Table 2 shows the role of educational institution. The results revealed that 61.4% of respondents agreed that the inculcation of national resources is a major challenge in the educational sector, 33.5% of respondents disagreed, 2.5% of respondents were neutral and 2.5% had no response. Majority of respondents (61.9%) agree that acquisition of appropriate skills and the development of social abilities are important for education quality and social transformation. 29.4% of respondents strongly agree with this statement, while 6.6% disagree and only 2% strongly disagree. In the case of the statement "Reduction of social vices," it appears that 45 respondents (22.8%) "strongly agree," 118 respondents (59.9%) "agree," 31 respondents (15.7%) "disagree," and 3 respondents (1.5%) "strongly disagree. Results indicate that a majority of respondents (61.9%) strongly agree that training the mind in the understanding of the world around is an important aspect of education. 37.1% of respondents agree with this statement, while only 1% and 0% of respondents disagree or strongly disagree with this statement respectively. Earlier support for these role had been provided in previous research (Nwajiuba and Igwe, 2020;)

TABLE 3: SOLUTIONS

Items	SA Freq(%)	A Freq(%)	D Freq(%)	SD Freq(%)	Mean ± SD
Give training and impact the necessary skills to individuals who shall be self-reliant economically	127(64.5)	65(33)	5(2.5)	0(0)	3.61 ± 0.53
Creating a research-friendly environment to encourage innovation	12(6.1)	121(61.4)	62(31.5)	2(1)	2.72 ± 0.58
Augment the salary structure of staff and include deserving benefits to limit brain drain and increase eagerness to impact knowledge in students	124(62.9)	72(36.5)	1(0.5)	0(0)	3.62 ± 0.49
Gender friendly education policy should be initiated	118(59.9)	74(37.6)	5(2.5)	0(0)	3.34 ± 0.47
More budget should be allocated to education and training programmes for teachers	89(45.2)	102(51.8)	5(2.5)	1(0.5)	3.57 ± 0.54
Revisit the recruitment policies to ensure that only qualified teachers are employed	57(28.9)	118(59.9)	13(6.6)	9(4.6)	3.13 ± 0.72
Government should ensure that only men and women of honest and proven integrity	132(67)	65(33)	0(0)	0(0)	3.67 ± 0.47

Weighted Mean =3.38

Table 3 revealed that 64.5% agreed that providing training and impacting the necessary skills to individuals can help them become self-reliant economically, 33% somewhat agreed, 2.5% were neutral, and there were 0 respondents who disagreed or strongly disagreed. The results of the survey suggest that a majority of the respondents 61.4% "strongly agree" or "agree" that creating a research-friendly environment to encourage innovation is important, while a smaller portion 31.5% are neutral on the matter and only 6.1% "strongly disagree" or "disagree". A

majority of the respondents (62.9%) "strongly agree" that augmenting the salary structure of staff and including deserving benefits is important to limit brain drain and increase eagerness to impact knowledge in students. Around 36.5% of respondents "agree" with this statement, while only 0.5% and 0% picked "strongly disagree" and "disagree". A majority of the respondents (59.9%) "strongly agree" that a gender-friendly education policy should be initiated, while a smaller portion (37.6%) agreed on the matter and only 2.5% "strongly disagree". 97% either "strongly agree" or "agree" that more budget should be allocated to education and training programs for teachers, with 45.2% "strongly agree" and 51.8% "agree". A smaller portion of the respondents (2.5%) disagreed, and only 0.5% "strongly disagree". The results of the survey suggest that a majority of the respondents (59.9%) "strongly agree" that the recruitment policies should be revisited to ensure that only qualified teachers are employed, while 28.9% of the respondents "agree" with this statement. On the other hand, 6.6% of the respondents disagreed and 4.6% "strongly disagree".

Conclusion and Recommendations

The importance of tertiary educational institutions has been espoused in this work, with major highlight bordering on the role it plays in the development and production of high-level manpower within the context of the needs of the nation. This research identified various problems faced by educational institutions in the country ranging from non adherence to quality assurance, administrative recklessness, reckless government policies, non commitment of government to confronting challenges in the educational sector, non-meritorious standard of recruitment etc. The study also highlighted several possible solutions as indicated by participants in the study; training and necessary skills of individuals who would be self-reliant economically, creation of a research-friendly environment to encourage innovation, augmentation of salary structure of staff and

include deserving benefits to limit brain drain, revisitation of the recruitment policies to ensure that only qualified staff are employed etc.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- Improving infrastructure: It is important to ensure that tertiary educational institutions have the appropriate infrastructure to support the various programs they offer.
- Encouraging research and innovation: A supportive environment that fosters research and innovation should be cultivated within tertiary educational institutions.
- Revising staff salaries: Revising staff salaries and providing incentives can help reduce brain drain and increase motivation to impart knowledge to students.
- Securing funding: The government should allocate adequate funds to the education sector to provide quality tertiary education.
- Collaborating with the private sector: Collaboration between the private and public sectors can help ensure that higher education institutions receive the necessary funding.
- Updating curricula and technology: Curricula and the use of technology should be updated to meet international standards.
- Improving library facilities: Tertiary educational institutions should provide well-equipped libraries with modern ICT equipment.
- Enhancing security: Tertiary educational institutions should implement measures to improve security and counter campus cultism.
- Impartial management: Management decisions should be made based on qualifications and not be influenced by political or partisan motives.

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